

NEW NEOLITHIC FIND IN THE SOUTHERN-EASTERN REGION OF NURATA MOUNTAINS (EXAMPLE OF AN ARROWHEAD FOUND IN THE KÖKTONLI AREA)

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Abstract. In October 2023, researchers from Samarkand Archaeological Institute conducted field surveys in Nurata mountain system (Nurata and Koshrabot districts). As a result, Neolithic sites named Kablyati, Chorvoqsoy, and Koktonli were identified. This article provides information on a green flint arrowhead, bifacially worked, found at the Koktonli site. Arrowheads of this type have been discovered during studies of the Hissar, Central Fergana, and Sazagon cultures, as well as in Neolithic communities of Kaltaminor culture. Similar arrowheads have also been studied in Mesolithic communities of the Caspian region. A similar bifacially worked arrowhead was found in Koratog, in the northern part of Nurata mountain range. This indicates strong cultural ties with the Neolithic culture of the Central Asian plains.

Keywords: Kaltaminor culture, Hissar culture, Sazagon culture, Central Fergana culture, Ustyurt Neolithic communities, Nurata mountain system, Neolithic, archaeological site, Koktonli, ancient spring, bifacial arrowhead.

Introduction. The study of human history began with the period of the primitive community. The lifestyle of ancient people began with great difficulties and people faced great difficulties in order to withstand the trials of nature and find food. They used stone tools to catch animals and began to learn how to make weapons from stones. These weapons were used for hunting and defense, and also played an important role in collecting and preparing food. Primitive people found ways to survive by making and using stone tools. The territory of Uzbekistan is considered one of the regions inhabited in different periods of the Stone Age. Among them are Nurata Mountains, which from a natural-geographical point of view are considered the northwestern branch of Turkestan Range. It is separated from Morguzar Range by Ilonatdi Gorge in Sangzor River Valley from the southeast, its southern border is Zarafshan Swamp, and the northern border adjoins the Kyzylkum Desert. In fact, Nurata Mountains consist of two parallel mountain ranges, called the Northern and Southern Nurata Mountains.

Definitely, Koytash Mountains are located in the southeastern part of the Northern Nurata Mountains. The average height of the central part is 1750 meters, and the height of the Zargartog Khaetboshi peak, considered its highest point, is 2169 meters. There are also such high peaks in this ridge as Katta Fozilman (2134 m), Karchigai (2105 m). The northwestern part of the Northern Nurata Mountains is not very high, its average height is 900-1100 meters. The Southern Nurata Ridge, considered the southern branch of Nurata Ridge, is cut by a series of meridional valleys consisting of streams originating from the Northern Nurata Ridge, extending from the southeast to the northwest. It consists of "bdingtog", "karakchitog" and "Oktog". Karatog in the northwest of Oktog is also part of the southern part of Nurata Mountains. These mountains are separated from each other by the territory of Gallaorol, Koshrabot and Nurata districts. Nurata Mountains extend to the northwest of the Ilon Otdi Gorge and consist of Paleozoic metamorphic rocks such

as limestone, sandstone and shale. The total length of this mountain range is 180 km, and the average height is 1000-1500 meters [1; Garyyev, 1968. -B. 44]. According to research, Nurata mountain range is one of the regions where human history has been developed since the Stone Age. Because these mountains attracted people with their favorable natural climate and rich flora and fauna. This is evidenced by the existence of many historical and cultural monuments of different stages of historical development and sources obtained during their study [2; Vafayev, Shpeneva, 1987, F.4. Op. 1. D.167; Kholmatov, 2017. -P. 42].

Besides that, further research has shown that Nurata mountain ranges are one of the territories that were exploited by mankind during the Neolithic period. It is known that the Neolithic period in Central Asia chronologically includes the 6th-4th millennia BC. During the Neolithic period, the number of types of weapons increased, including: stone axes, ponas, stone awls, awls, bow arrowheads, heavy flails. In Central Asia, there were 2 different types of development of the Neolithic community:

1. The first agricultural culture was formed in the southwestern regions, in the basins of the mountain rivers of Kopetdog on the territory of modern Turkmenistan.

2. In the central and northern regions, Neolithic communities were engaged in hunting and fishing. The specifics of interregional development are due to natural and climatic conditions.

Additionally, in Central Asia, the monuments of the Neolithic period are divided into several economic forms: among them are the Joytun culture, the Kaltaminor culture, the Gissar culture and the Sazagon culture, the Central Fergana culture and the Ustyurt Neolithic communities. Joytun culture is a monument of the first agricultural tribes of the southwestern region of Central Asia. Its traces have been found only in the southwestern regions of Turkmenistan. Scientists believe that it dates back to the end of the 6th - beginning of the 5th millennium BC. It was studied by B. A. Kufin, V. M. Masson, D. Durdyev, O. Berdiev. Joytun culture includes settlements of a number of primitive farmers, such as Bami, Togoloktepa, Chagllitepa, Munchoklitepa, Chopontepa, Joytun, Naizatepa. The Kaltaminor culture is widespread in the western and northwestern parts of Central Asia. Its northwestern border extends to the middle and lower reaches of Ural River, and its western border to Caspian Sea. It reaches the foothills of the Karakum and Kyzylkum deserts in the south and the Lower Syr Darya on the northern, eastern and southern shores of the Aral Sea in the east. The Kaltaminor culture is also widespread in the vast territory of the Kyzylkum and Ustyurt deserts.

Moreover, the Hissar culture is a culture of tribes living in mountainous areas and mainly engaged in hunting animals. It is widespread in the mountainous regions of Tajikistan. Their traces have been found in more than 300 places. The first monument of this culture was found in the Hissar Valley near the city of Dushanbe, so it was called the Hissar culture.

It should be mentioned that the cultural sites of Sazagon (Sazagon 1, 2, Tepakol 3) are located 30 km southwest of Samarkand in the middle basin of Zarafshan River. Many stone tools of the Neolithic era and animal bones were found in Sazagon. The inhabitants of the Sazagon culture lived in mountainous areas and were mainly engaged in hunting animals. For this reason, during excavations of the premises, along with tools adapted for hunting, bone remains of wild and domestic animals were also found in its upper layers.

The monuments of Central Fergana are monuments of the early Neolithic period, studied in the 50s of the 20th centuries. They were found in the deserts of central Fergana, and to date more than 80 sites have been identified. They are widely known as the Central Fergana culture.

Neolithic sites have been discovered in the Karakalpak steppe, Mingbulok, Saryksuv, Okum, Damkol and Kyzyltepa districts. Their list includes Zam bar 1,2, Yangikadam 12,14, 16,19, 35, Mingbulok, Saryksuv, Uzunkol, Dorozkol, Madvor and others. [3; Egamberdieva N.A. 2011 b 53-59]

Hunting and Provisioning: Bow arrowheads show that ancient people were engaged in hunting, which indicates the resources they used for provisioning.

Cultural Links: The distribution of stone tools and their structure indicate the presence of cultural links between regions. More detailed information about these cultural links can be obtained by comparing them with arrowheads found in other regions.

The Role of Mountainous Areas: The fact that sites such as Koktonly, located on the mountain plains in the southeastern region of Nurata region, were important for ancient societies creates an understanding of the unique ecological and resource potential of these areas.

It should be mentioned that a bow arrowhead known to us from the Koktonli site was found on the side terrace of the stream. (Fig. 1). The size of the green flint bow tip: 2.7x1.8x0.5 mm. Double-sided. As is known, identical arrowheads were found in the monuments of Sazagón 1 and Sazagón 2, as well as in the monuments of Jangal 1. Both sides were treated with the method of parallel retouching. This is a technique of processing and retouching, called secondary processing.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Several hundred double-edged arrowheads from the Neolithic era have been found in Central Asia. In Tajikistan, they are known from the materials of the settlements of Kukhnya, Kurtek (Markansuva culture), and Ok-Tanga (Gisor culture). [6; Ranov V. A. 1958 b 24-26, 28, 29,] There are no monuments of the Neolithic era that have preserved the cultural layer in Central Fergana; about 10 arrowheads have been collected from scattered settlements. Among them are two-handed weapons and retouched objects from near Hisar and Markansuva, but unlike the finds from Tajikistan, there are more single-handed ones here. In the Kyzylkum Desert, in the main territory where the monuments of the Kaltaminor cultural community are scattered, double-edged arrowheads originating from the cultural layer are known only from the settlements of the ancient Okchadarya delta. At one time it was found in Jonbas 4, Kavaf 7 and Tolstovsky district [7; Vinogradov A. B. 1979, pp. 122, 129-131]. Both ends have a leaf-shaped form, and the base is covered with light grooves. As a result of excavations at the Kaskajol burial ground in the southeast of Ustyurt, a number of arrowheads of Central Asian significance were found, which are now identified as belonging to the late Neolithic era. The study of the findings was considered in the works of V. N. Yagodin and E. B. Bizhanov [8; Bizhanov E. B. 1985, pp. 250-252]. Most of the arrowheads found in Kaskajol have a leaf-shaped form (in some cases leaning towards a rhombus) with light, sometimes barely noticeable grooves at the base.

As for the findings from the Sazagón culture sites, these findings also belong to the culture of the "mountain Neolithic" period. Eight arrowheads have been found here so far. One was found at the Sazag'on 1 site from the late Mesolithic, five - at the site Sazag'on 2 from the late Mesolithic - early Neolithic. Two stone bow arrows were also found at the site Jangal 1. (Fig. 3, 1-8) If we talk about the uniqueness of the Sazagón site, then, first of all, it completely lacks stone weapons with one-sided retouching of the edge, and the weapons found at three settlements can be attributed to the double-sided processed types. Six tools have a leaf-shaped form (various variants are presented), two are close to diamond-shaped (the corners are slightly flattened) (Fig. 3. 3-4). The area of impact is rounded or slightly curved. On this basis, the tip is sharply distinguished by parallel retouches marked on the side of the raw material (Fig. 3-5). Despite the widespread use of crushing techniques, most Sazagón Mako bow arrowheads show some archaic features.

In conclusion, it can be summarized that the Koktonly area has been one of the areas of human communities since ancient times, like the Hissar, Central Fergana and Sazagon cultures, as well as Kaltaminor. It should be said that the stone weapons found at the Koktonly settlement in the northern part of Nurata mountain range, as well as the arrowhead of a bow made of green flint, two-handed bows studied at the settlements of Jangal, Sazagon-1, Sazagon-2, are similar to arrowheads and provide information about the technological knowledge and cultural life of people of ancient times. This finding is of great importance not only for archaeological research, but also for understanding the development of society. Due to these findings, we will have the opportunity to better understand the life of ancient people, their technological and cultural development. These studies help to better understand not only the ancient history of Uzbekistan, but also the evolutionary and migration path of mankind. Archaeological findings found in these areas increase the historical significance of the entire region and are of great interest to the scientific community.

REFERENCES

1. Koriev M. Natural Geography of Central Asia. - Tashkent, 1968, p.-44.
2. Vafaev G.A., Shpeneva L.Yu. Report on the compilation of monuments of the Koshrabad district of the Samarkand region // UzRFA Archaeology of the Institute of Ilmiki Archives. F.4., .1. D.167. - Samarkand, 1987.
3. Egamberdieva N.A. Archaeology T.2011- 2023
4. Marie-Louise Inizan, Michel Reduron-Ballenger, Helene Roche, Jacques Tixier, Technologie e d e la pierre e Taille e, Published with the conferences of the National Scientific Research Centre and the University of Paris X Nanterre 1995. b- 31
5. Ranov V. A. Study of Stone Age monuments in the Eastern Pamirs in 1958. // TIAN of the Tajik SSR. 1961. Vol. XXVII.
6. Vinogradov A. B. On the distribution of Kelteminar type nozzles // Ethnography and archeology of Central Asia. Moscow: Nauka, 1979;
7. Vinogradov A. V. Ancient hunters and fishermen of the Central Asian interfluve // TE. 1981.
8. Bizhanov E. B. Neolithic burial on Ustyurt // Sa. 1985. No. 1.
9. Kholmatov N. U. (Samarkand). Double-sided processed arrowheads in the Neolithic of Central Asia. Soviet archeology 1991.